

FORMATION OF MOTOR SKILLS BY WEIGHTLIFTING IN THE PROCESS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Annotation: The article presents the results obtained during testing the effectiveness of an experimental program for the formation of students' motor skills in the process of physical education using weightlifting.

Key words: weightlifting, students, motor skills.

Introduction. The main directions of transformation of modern higher education are impossible without finding new, effective ways to optimize the professional training of specialists in the field of physical education [1, 2, 4].

For many reasons, in the field of physical education in higher education, many unresolved problems and issues have accumulated that attract the attention of domestic scientists. Thus, the problems of increasing students' interest in physical education classes have been studied by some scientists [3, 5, 6, 7].

Despite a significant amount of recent research on the issues of professional training of teaching staff and issues related to improving the content of education, these problems today are still far from being resolved [8, 10, 11]. Physical education in higher education is a pedagogical process designed to solve such problems as maintaining and enhancing health, developing physical abilities, equipping students with special knowledge for their use of various means and methods of individual development.

Analysis, generalization and systematization of educational, methodological and special literature on the problems of introducing various means and methods of

physical education into the educational process of students indicates the growing interest and active work of scientists in this direction [9, 12, 13].

Studies have been conducted to determine the effectiveness of the influence of systematic volleyball training on the body of female students, the formation of the motor function of girls during sports games, the influence of athletics on the physical fitness.

Increasing demands on the health of the nation require a large number of highly qualified physical education specialists who were able to use modern scientific and methodological materials in their work and implement the achievements of scientists and leading students into practice [14, 15, 16].

Today, strength sports have become very popular. It is power sports that contribute to the manifestation of a person's maximum strength efforts due to developed active muscle mass, increased performance, improved health, and building a beautiful physique [17, 18]. Among strength sports, the first place is occupied by weightlifting, which is an Olympic sport. New types such as bodybuilding, powerlifting, mountain sports, arm wrestling, athleticism, shaping, and fitness are becoming more and more widespread. In our opinion, the arsenal of means and experience accumulated in strength sports is not sufficiently used when working on physical education.

An alarming situation has developed in the Republic of Uzbekistan, posing a great threat to national security, social and demographic spheres. The critical level of health, physical fitness and physical development of pupils and students is a consequence of a decrease in their lever activity in the daily routine with increasing static and psycho-emotional stress of learning, and the introduction of innovative technologies. under normal environmental conditions [19, 20].

It is physical education, as an integral component of the educational process, that can help improve performance, strengthen and preserve the health of children and youth. Taking this into account, an important role in the educational process of a modern school is assigned to the activities of a physical education teacher who is

able to demonstrate the contradictions of physical development, increase the level of motor activity of young people, and implement their professional skills at a high level [21].

Physical education as an integral part of the general education system in the educational sphere of children and youth should be conceptualized to strengthen physical and mental health, an integrated approach to the formation of mental and motor qualities of personal activity on the principles of an individual approach, the priority of a health-improving focus, the widespread use of various methods and forms of physical improvement.

Strength exercises are considered one of the most powerful means of health training. To prevent the development of degenerative changes in the musculoskeletal system (arthrosis, osteochondrosis), as well as to treat these diseases, it is recommended to include strength exercises in various load modes in a comprehensive health training. For overweight persons they are performed in the mode of reducing adipose tissue, and for persons with insufficient body weight and poor physical development - in the mode of increasing muscle mass. These exercises serve as a means of developing strength endurance and preventing injuries to the musculoskeletal system.

Experimental model of a training program for the discipline "Athleticism and yoga teaching techniques." The fundamental difference between the experimental program using weightlifting means is in the formation of students' motor skills in the process of physical education. By weightlifting means we mean classical and auxiliary exercises. Classic exercises include: bench press, snatch and push of the barbell with two hands. Auxiliary exercises are divided into special and general developmental. Special exercises are a means of improving the elements of the technique of classical exercises, as well as developing strength, speed abilities, flexibility and agility. General developmental exercises are used to increase the level of general physical fitness of students and develop physical abilities.

Strength abilities are characterized by the fact that the dominant role in their detection is played by the activation of muscle tension processes, stimulated by external weights (resistance). Some of the manifestations of speed-strength abilities are called “explosive strength”, the ability, along the way of movement, to achieve the greatest possible indicators of external manifestation of force in the shortest time. Under the influence of physical exercise, physiological mechanisms are trained that contribute to the development of muscle strength by improving intramuscular and intermuscular coordination of motor and autonomic functions. These include: an increase in the degree of mobilization in antagonist muscles of motor units, inhibition of the activity of synergistic muscles and the entry into muscles through the central nervous system of impulses from the sympathetic nervous system. Muscle strength can be developed with both dynamic and static exercises. Dynamic strength in our study was determined by the test of flexion and extension of the arms in a lying position and raising the torso.

Conclusions. The results of testing strength abilities at the beginning and end of the experiment prove the effectiveness of the proposed experimental methodology for the formation of motor skills in the process of physical education by means of weightlifting. A promising direction for further research may be the formation of students’ motor skills through weightlifting using our methods in other sports specializations, taking into account gender characteristics and socio-psychological factors.

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